

evaluated by the equation,
 $-\Delta F = -2.303 RT \log K_s$. Stability constant and free energy of the complexes are given in Table 1.

Ir spectral studies: The point of attachment of the ligand with the metal ion has been confirmed by studying the infrared spectrum of the ligand and the isolated chelates.

The strong bond appearing at 1700 cm^{-1} ($\text{C}=\text{O}$) in the ligand is shifted to lower frequency at 1630 - 1690 cm^{-1} on complexation in all the systems, suggesting the formation of $\text{C}-\text{O}-\text{M}$ bonding. The strong bond at 1630 cm^{-1} in the ligand was assigned to azomethine group. On complexation, this gets lowered to 1590 - 1610 cm^{-1} indicating the formation of $\text{M}-\text{N}$ bond. Hence, it is concluded that coordination occurs through $\text{CH}=\text{N}$ and $\text{C}=\text{O}$ group. A peak observed at 3400 cm^{-1} (OH) in the ligand vanishes on complexation; therefore, it is concluded that the third point of attachment of metal to ligand occurs through the oxygen atom of OH group of the ligand.

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Isolation of Halogeno and Complex-halogeno Anions as Salts of Oxinate Chelates of Bis(cyclopentadienyl)-titanium(IV) and -zirconium(IV)

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DOYLE and Tobias¹ pointed out that coordination of four oxygen atoms by strong covalent bonds to $\text{Cp}_2\text{M}^{2+}(\text{IV})$ moiety ($\text{M}=\text{Ti}, \text{V}$) would lead to weakening of the metal-ring bonds. In order to investigate, whether or not the coordination of two nitrogen and two oxygen atoms around the titanium(IV)/zirconium(IV) ion would produce a similar weakening of the metal-ring bonds, we studied the interaction of $\text{Cp}_2\text{TiCl}_2/\text{Cp}_2\text{ZrCl}_2$ with 8-quinolinol in aqueous medium. We failed to isolate derivatives in which two 8-quinolate groups coordinated to the Cp_2M^{2+} ($\text{M}=\text{Ti}^{IV}, \text{Zr}^{IV}$). However, ionic complexes of the type, $[\text{Cp}_2\text{M}(\text{8-quinolinol})]^+\text{Cl}^-$ in which only one bidentate 8-quinolate group is coordinated to the Ti -

ium(IV)/zirconium(IV) ion are readily obtained. A number of halogeno and complex-halogeno salts of these complexes of the type $[\text{Cp}_2\text{M}(\text{8-quinolinol})]^+\text{X}^-$ ($\text{M}=\text{Ti}$ or Zr ; $\text{X}^-=\text{Br}^-, \text{I}^-, \text{CuCl}_2^-, \text{ZnCl}_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})^-, \text{CdCl}_2^-, \text{HgCl}_2^+$) have been isolated in aqueous medium and characterised.

Experimental

All reagents used were of analytical grade. Nitrogen and halogens were determined by standard gravimetric methods². Conductance measurements were made in nitrobenzene at $30 \pm 0.05^\circ$ with a Systronic 304 digital direct reading conductivity meter. Infrared spectra (KBr) were recorded in the region 4000 - 200 cm^{-1} with a Perkin-Elmer 621 grating spectrophotometer. ^1H nmr spectra were recorded in deuterated acetone at a sweep width of 900 Hz with a Perkin-Elmer R-32 spectrophotometer. Chemical shifts are expressed relative to an internal reference of TMS (1% by volume).

Preparation of complexes: An aqueous solution of $[\text{Cp}_2\text{Ti}(\text{8-quinolinol})]^+\text{Cl}^-/[\text{Cp}_2\text{Zr}(\text{8-quinolinol})]^+\text{Cl}^-$ was obtained by stirring an aqueous solution of $\text{Cp}_2\text{TiCl}_2/\text{Cp}_2\text{ZrCl}_2$ with an excess of solid 8-quinolinol for about 1 h. The solution was filtered and the filtrate added separately to a hot solution of KBr, KI, CuCl_2 , ZnCl_2 , CdCl_2 and HgCl_2 . The solution was digested over water-bath for 4 h. Ionic complexes of the type, $[\text{Cp}_2\text{Ti}(\text{8-quinolinol})]^+\text{X}^-$ and $[\text{Cp}_2\text{Zr}(\text{8-quinolinol})]^+\text{X}^-$ ($\text{X}^-=\text{Br}^-, \text{I}^-, \text{CuCl}_2^-, \text{ZnCl}_2^-, \text{CdCl}_2^+$ and HgCl_2^+ , respectively) were precipitated. These were filtered and washed with petroleum ether.

Results and discussion

Table 1 lists the analytical data and physical characteristics of the complexes. The complexes are thermally stable and decompose at higher temperatures without melting. They are soluble in acetone and THF, and partially soluble in chloroform and dichloromethane. With ZnCl_2 , an aquotrichlorozincate(II) anion, $[\text{Cp}_2\text{M}(\text{8-quinolinol})]^+\text{ZnCl}_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})^-$ is precipitated. The presence of coordinated water is identified by its intense infrared absorption at $\sim 3450 \text{ cm}^{-1}$. Conductivity measurements show that all the complexes except CdCl_2^+ salts are 1:1 electrolytes in nitrobenzene. However, in case of CdCl_2^+ salts, the results are consistent with those of 1:2 electrolytes, indicating that the dinegative anions are precipitated.

Infrared spectra: No halide bridging is observed in halide and complexhalo anion salts. The frequencies at 350 - 370 cm^{-1} region for complex-halogeno salts are characteristic of complex chloro anions^{1,2}. A strong band at 1500 cm^{-1} in the free 8-hydroxyquinoline may be assigned to $\text{C}=\text{N}$ bond. In complexes, this band is shifted to lower wavenumber at $\sim 1330 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ indicating the coordination of nitrogen atom of 8-hydroxyquinoline ligand to the metal⁴. Further, in the spectra of complexes,

NOTES

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL DATA AND PHYSICAL CHARACTERISTICS

Sl. no.	Compd.	Colour	Dec. temp. °C	Conduc-tance* $\Omega^{-1}\text{cm}^2\text{mol}^{-1}$	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.) N	Halogen
1.	$[\text{Cp}_2\text{Ti}(\text{8-quinolinol})]^+\text{Br}^-$	Yellow	215-216	29.8	3.32 (3.48)	19.93 (19.89)
2.	$[\text{Cp}_2\text{Ti}(\text{8-quinolinol})]^+\text{I}^-$	Yellow	185-187	28.6	3.10 (3.12)	28.22 (28.28)
3.	$[\text{Cp}_2\text{Ti}(\text{8-quinolinol})]^+\text{CuCl}_2^-$	Green	98-100	30.2	2.80 (2.85)	21.61 (21.65)
4.	$[\text{Cp}_2\text{Ti}(\text{8-quinolinol})]^+\text{ZnCl}_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})^-$	Greenish yellow	210-212	30.4	2.56 (2.74)	20.64 (20.81)
5.	$[\text{Cp}_2\text{Ti}(\text{8-quinolinol})]_2\text{CdCl}_2^-$	Yellow	278-280	50.2	2.60 (2.77)	14.20 (14.05)
6.	$[\text{Cp}_2\text{Ti}(\text{8-quinolinol})]^+\text{HgCl}_2^-$	Yellow	140-142	30.0	2.08 (2.23)	16.80 (16.93)
7.	$[\text{Cp}_2\text{Zr}(\text{8-quinolinol})]^+\text{Br}^-$	Green	280-282	28.8	3.01 (3.15)	17.82 (17.95)
8.	$[\text{Cp}_2\text{Zr}(\text{8-quinolinol})]^+\text{I}^-$	Green	216-218	28.6	2.68 (2.84)	25.82 (25.79)
9.	$\text{Cp}_2\text{Zr}(\text{8-quinolinol})^+\text{CuCl}_2^-$	Yellowish green	158-160	30.2	2.50 (2.62)	19.86 (19.90)
10.	$[\text{Cp}_2\text{Zr}(\text{8-quinolinol})]^+\text{ZnCl}_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})^-$	Green	218-220	31.2	2.41 (2.53)	19.12 (19.25)
11.	$[\text{Cp}_2\text{Zr}(\text{8-quinolinol})]_2\text{CdCl}_2^-$	Yellowish green	146-150	50.6	2.49 (2.66)	13.32 (13.47)
12.	$[\text{Cp}_2\text{Zr}(\text{8-quinolinol})]^+\text{HgCl}_2^-$	Yellowish green	176-178	28.8	2.01 (2.08)	15.71 (15.84)

* $0.50 \times 10^4 \text{ M}$

disappearance of the broad $\nu_{\text{O-H}}$ at $3\ 600\text{--}3\ 560\ \text{cm}^{-1}$ and appearance of a medium intensity band at $520\ \text{cm}^{-1}$ due to $\nu_{\text{C-O}}$ show the deprotonation of phenolic OH group and bonding of the 8-hydroxy-quinoline ligand to the metal through phenolic oxygen⁶.

The bands occurring consistently around $3\ 080$ (C—H stretch), $1\ 430$ (asymmetric ring breathing), $1\ 080$ (C—H deformation of C_8H_8 ring) and $815\ \text{cm}^{-1}$ (C—H bending out-of-plane deformation) in all the complexes suggest the presence of η^5 -cyclopentadienyl ring⁶. An additional band near $440\ \text{cm}^{-1}$ may be assigned to $\text{M-C}_8\text{H}_8$ vibrations⁷.

Pmr spectra : ^1H nmr spectra of the complexes were recorded in deuterated acetone. The spectra of free oxine show the signals at $\delta\ 7.31$ (4H, m), 8.05 (1H, q, $J\ 9.0$ and 2.5 Hz) and 8.73 (1H, q, $J\ 4.0$ and 1.6 Hz) due to the $\text{C}_{8,6,6,7}$, C_4 and C_2 protons, respectively. In the metal complexes, however, the former two signals (due to the $\text{C}_{8,6,6,7}$ and C_4) are not separately identifiable and resulting in a complex multiplet in the region $\delta\ 7.4\text{--}8.2$. The resonance due to the C_2 protons is at $\delta\ 9.06$ (q, $J\ 4.0$ and 1.8 Hz). The fact that it is shifted downfield with respect to the free oxine, supports the conclusion that the oxinate ligand is chelating. The spectra of the $\text{ZnCl}_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})^-$ salts show an additional resonance signal due to the presence of a coordinated water molecules at $\delta\ 4.18$. The resonance signals due to C_8H_8 group is observed as a singlet at $\delta\ 6.7$.

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Five- and Six-coordinate Low-spin Iron(III) Complexes

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IRON(III) is known to form high-spin, ($S=5/2$) low-spin ($S=1/2$) and intermediate-spin ($S=3/2$) complexes under the influence of different ligand fields. Spin-crossover phenomenon is usually observed with the iron(III) compounds. Examples of high-spin and spin-crossover compounds of iron(III) are numerous. However, there exists limited examples of low-spin iron(III) complexes. In continuation to our studies on iron(III)¹, we report in